

A facile method for the synthesis of 2-aryl-7-methylpyrano[4,3-*b*]pyran-4,5[4*H*,5*H*]-diones[†]

Om Prakash, Ajay Kumar and Shiv P. Singh*

Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, India

E-mail : shivpsingh@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-1744-238628, 238277

Manuscript received 3 September 2003

The reaction of substituted 3-cinnamoyl-4-hydroxypyran-2[2*H*]-ones (**3a-h**) in I₂/DMSO provides a facile method for the synthesis of 2-aryl-7-methylpyrano[4,3-*b*]pyran-4,5[4*H*,5*H*]-diones (**2a-h**).

Pyranopyran-4,5-diones of the type **1** and **2** are important both from synthetic and biological points of view¹. In contrast to the several methods^{2,3} available for the synthesis of 7-substituted-2-alkylpyrano[4,3-*b*]pyran-4,5[4*H*,5*H*]-diones (**1**, chromone analogs of dehydroacetic acid, DHA), there is only one report⁴ which describes the synthesis of the corresponding 2-aryl derivatives (**2**, flavone analogs of DHA). The reported synthesis of five compounds of the type **2**, consists of two steps : (i) conversion of 3-cinnamoyl-4-hydroxypyran-2[2*H*]-ones (**3**, chalcone⁵ analogs of DHA) into the corresponding dibromo derivative **4** by the reaction with bromine, (ii) base catalysed cyclodehydrobromination of **4** into **2**.

In view of these observations and our ongoing interest in the chemistry of DHA and its derivatives^{6,7}, it was considered worthwhile to develop a simple procedure for the synthesis of **2**. We report in this communication a one-step process, which is not only facile but also avoids the use of highly hazardous bromine. This method consists of treating **3** with DMSO/I₂, which has effectively been employed earlier for the synthesis^{8,9} of several flavone derivatives, for the synthesis of title compounds (**2**) (Scheme 1).

In order to attempt the proposed method, **3a**, available by the condensation of DHA with benzaldehyde in the presence of piperidine was treated with I₂/DMSO according to the condition used for flavone derivatives. The reaction afforded the expected product (**2a**) in 55% yield. Using the same procedure, other known cinnamoyl derivatives were also converted into the corresponding **2b-d** in 50–60% yields (Table I).

In the light of these promising results, we decided to extend this synthetic approach to the synthesis of some new derivatives **2e-h**. The method was found to be successful as

Scheme 1

chalcone analogs of DHA, **3e-h** underwent smooth cyclization to the corresponding **2e-h**. The known products were identified by the comparison of m.ps. with those reported in the literature. The structures of the products were also confirmed by their spectral data. Compounds **2a-h** exhibited carbonyl absorptions in the regions 1720–1750 and 1620–1640 cm⁻¹ respectively, for the 2-pyrone and 4-pyrone rings.

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji for his contribution to this Department.

Table 1. Pyranopyrandonones **2a-h**, prepared according to Scheme 1

Pyranopyrans	M.p. (°C) (Lit. m.p.) ^d	Yield (%) ^a	Molecular formula
2a	260–61 (265)	55 (52)	<i>b</i>
2b	150–51 (160)	58 (54)	<i>b</i>
2c	168–69 (170)	50 (53)	<i>b</i>
2d	211–12 (215)	56 (51)	<i>b</i>
2e	172–73	53	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ ^f
2f	158–59	58	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClO ₄ ^f
2g	180–82	56	C ₁₅ H ₉ FO ₄ ^f
2h	122–123	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₅ ^f

^aYields of isolated products w.r.t. the quantity of chalcone analog **3**.

^bSpectral properties (IR, ¹H NMR and MS) were in full agreement with those reported previously.

^cElemental analyses (C, H) were satisfactory.

The characteristic signal in the PMR spectra (TFA) at δ 6.1 (s) shows the proton of flavone analog at position 3 in the structure **2**.

In conclusion, the present study provides an efficient and general one step procedure for the synthesis of title compounds **2a-h**. Yields of products in the present study are comparable with reported method, but I₂/DMSO procedure is superior in terms of time, simplicity and use of eco-friendly reagents.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 300 MHz instrument using TMS as an internal standard. Chalcone analogs **3a-h** were prepared according to literature procedure⁵.

General procedure for the conversion of substituted 3-cinnamoyl-4-hydroxypyran-2[2H]-ones (3a-h) to 2-aryl-7-methylpyrano[4,3-b]pyran-4,5[4H,5H]-diones (2a-h) :

To a solution of **3** (1 mmol) in dry DMSO (15 ml) was added 2–3 crystals of iodine and the mixture was heated under reflux for 3–4 h. The excess solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the resulting mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature. Then solution was poured in ice-cold water. The solid product **2** was filtered, washed successively with sodium metabisulphite solution,

the resulting solid washed with water, ethanol and chloroform.

2-(4-Methyl)phenyl-7-methylpyrano[4,3-b]pyran-4,5[4H,5H]-diones (2e) :

IR (KBr) (ν cm⁻¹) 1742, 1637; ¹H NMR (TFA, CDCl₃) δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.8 (1H, s), 6.1 (1H, s), 7.0 (2H, d, arom), 7.4 (2H, d, arom).

2-(4-Chloro)phenyl-7-methylpyrano[4,3-b]pyran-4,5[4H,5H]-diones (2f) :

IR (KBr) (ν cm⁻¹) 1745, 1632; ¹H NMR (TFA, CDCl₃) δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.9 (1H, s), 6.3 (1H, s), 7.1 (2H, d, arom), 7.5 (2H, d, arom).

2-(4-Fluoro)phenyl-7-methylpyrano[4,3-b]pyran-4,5[4H,5H]-diones (2g) :

IR (KBr) (ν cm⁻¹) 1745, 1631; ¹H NMR (TFA, CDCl₃) δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.8 (1H, s), 6.2 (1H, s), 6.8 (2H, d, arom), 7.2 (2H, d, arom).

2-(2-Methoxy)phenyl-7-methylpyrano[4,3-b]pyran-4,5[4H,5H]-diones (2h) :

IR (KBr) (ν cm⁻¹) 1740, 1634; ¹H NMR (TFA, CDCl₃) δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.7 (1H, s), 6.0 (1H, s), 6.8–7.4 (4H, m, arom).

Acknowledgement

The work reported here has been supported through DRDO Extramural Basic Research Grant No. ERIP/ER/0103294/M/01 and is subject to sponsor's disclaimer.

References

1. T. Money, *Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **70**, 553.
2. P. F. G. Praill, A. W. Khan and M. Siddiq, *J. Chem. Soc. (Pak)*, 1985, 59.
3. O. Caputo, L. Cattel, F. Viola and G. Biglino, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1977, **107**, 455.
4. M. Siddiq and Y. Qamar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 373.
5. R. H. Wiley, C. H. Jarboe and H. G. Elert, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5102.
6. O. Prakash, A. Kumar, A. Sadana and Shiv P. Singh, *Synth. Commun.*, 2002, **32**, 2663.
7. Shiv P. Singh, O. Prakash and R. K. Vaid, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 191.
8. W. Fatma, J. Iqbal, H. Ismail, K. Ishratullah, W. A. Shaida and W. Rahman, *Chem. Ind.*, 1979, 315.
9. W. Fatma, J. Iqbal, V. Manchanda, W. A. Shaida and W. Rahman, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1984, 298; *(M)* 1984, 2656.